

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

BLENDED LEARNING AND ITS TYPES. COMPARISON OF POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE QUALITIES

Bashlinskaya F.

Master student of Baku State University

ABSTRACT

In connection with the increasing role of continuous education, there are more and more different approaches to the conduct of the educational process. In this paper, the main types of blended learning are considered and an analysis of the positive and negative qualities of each of them is carried out.

Keywords: blended learning, inverted classroom, autonomous groups, change of working areas, personal choice, individual curriculum, self-development, independent work, educational technologies.

This work was supported by the Science Development Foundation under the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan – Grant № EIF-GAT-6-2021-2(39)-13/01/1-M-01

Mixed education is understood as a method of conducting the educational process, in which the traditional model of education is integrated with modern information technologies, because of which mobility, accessibility and digestibility of the material being studied increases.

For the first time the use of educational technologies was proposed by H. Skinner in 1866². Skinner patented the apparatus "Teaching Spelling", which allows you to train the spelling of words, as well as their reading. Further, attempts to introduce training devices were made by H. A. Akins (1913) and S. L. Pressi (1928), but in those days they were not successful.

With the advent of computer technology, the concept of blended learning became more possible. The first computers used for educational purposes were MARK 1 (Harvard) and ENIAC (University of Pennsylvania) were created respectively, in 1944 and 1946. They were used in the study of mathematics and engineering as a mathematical apparatus for solving problems³.

In 1960, Donald L. Bitzer developed the PLATO computer program, which was used "as an educational tool"⁴ and which laid the foundation for online communities. By the 80s, the program had become widely used in the global educational space.

The process of introducing information technology is becoming increasingly important every day. Today, due to the widespread use of the Internet and computer technologies, the learning process can be organized in such a way as to achieve its greatest efficiency. Thus, the following types of blended learning can be distinguished⁵:

1. Inverted classroom
2. Autonomous groups
3. Change of working areas
4. Personal choice
5. Individual curriculum

The first three models are applied to large groups focused on compulsory learning. Models 4, 5 are applicable to students individually, depending on their desire.

1. Flipped class.

This method of teaching consists in the fact that new material is independently studied by students, with the help of training video lectures and material specially prepared by the teacher. Class time is allocated for direct work with the teacher, consolidation of the material, clarification of incomprehensible topics, practical work.

According to the study in mathematics for electrical engineering students⁶, the inverted class method showed positive results. So, according to teachers, it is possible to get feedback from students, and most of the time is devoted to individual practice: "In classes conducted using an inverted classroom, the teacher spends approximately 40% of the time explaining, the remaining 60% of the time is used for individual practice. This is a significant change from traditional lectures, where 75% of the time was used by the teacher to present the content." However, there were difficulties when working with students who did not prepare for the lesson in advance and did not watch the lecture. Most students also left positive feedback.

Advantages	Disadvantages
More time is devoted to practice	It is necessary to prepare video lessons and other materials in advance

² "A History of Teaching Machines" Ludy T. Benjamin, Jr Texas A&M University.

³ THE journal. "Computers in Education: A Brief History.

⁴ PLATO, computer-based education system. Steve Jones

⁵ «История развития образовательных моделей и технологий» Е.А.Алисов, Л.С. Подымова, Москва, Берлин 2021.

⁶ Inverted Classroom by Topic - A Study in Mathematics for Electrical Engineering Students, PAPER INVERTED CLASSROOM BY TOPIC – A STUDY IN MATHEMATICS FOR ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING STUDENTS, I. Braun, S. Ritter and M. Vasko Karlsruhe University of Applied Sciences, Karlsruhe, Germany.

Students can study the material at a convenient time, and at a convenient pace	Different levels of training of students
New material is presented in video format, which facilitates perception	There are students who, for one reason or another, are not able to study the material in advance.
Develop the skills of reasoning and independent study	It is difficult to organize the process with a large number of students

Thus, when using this method, it is necessary to strongly motivate students and their awareness of the importance of independent work.

2. Change of working areas.

This method is based on the division of students into groups, each of which works in a pre-prepared working area. As a rule, the most effective is the division into three groups:⁷

- A group working with a teacher;
- Individual work at the computer;

Practical activity.

Each student, during the lesson, necessarily works in each zone.

The method can be used in conjunction with the Inverted Class method. In addition, the number of groups and "zones" are determined by the teacher and students in advance.⁸

The main advantages and disadvantages of this method include the following features⁹:

Advantages	Disadvantages
Increasing the motivation and interest of students in the educational process due to the change of work activities;	The difficulty of organizing the teaching process and the process of preparing for the lesson;
The possibility of an individualized approach to students through work with small groups;	The need for a large number of specially trained technologies.
Reducing the fatigue of students due to a change of activity;	The need for preliminary preparation of students for a new method of education.
Development of communication skills.	

3. Autonomous groups.

The method of teaching an autonomous class consists in dividing the class (group, collective) into two groups, one of which implies independent learning within the framework of the educational process; the second group takes a lesson on the classical system of education.

The peculiarity of the method is that an autonomous group studies all the information provided by various (book, Internet) sources, and after self-study, a lesson is held with a teacher aimed at satisfying students' questions. The second group conducts a full-time lesson with a teacher, which gives more basic information.

Advantages	Disadvantages
Development of independence in a student;	The likelihood of problems with finding information on the Internet, due to technical problems;
An opportunity for more advanced students to learn at their own pace;	Varying degrees of mastery of students' knowledge;
Wide range of information provided;	The possibility of losing the right direction of development due to a large amount of information;
Possibility of assistance from the teacher, in the future, answers to the necessary questions	

4. Personal choice.

The "personal choice" blended learning model differs from other models by the student's complete immersion in the industry he is interested in. This model of learning is intended mainly for high school students, as it assumes a formed consciousness for a responsible independent search for material.

Mandatory, for this model of training, is the full individual support of the student, at the entire stage of training, both pedagogical and psychological.

Depending on the scale of the classes, two areas can be distinguished:

A new profile.

A group of students is formed from students of different classes of one educational institution, in order to

⁷ Технологические особенности модели "смена рабочих зон", <https://canvas.instructure.com/courses/1189709/pages/tiekhnologhichieskiie-osobiennosti-modieli-smiena-rabochikh-zon>

⁸ APPLICATION OF THE ROTATION MODEL FROM MIXED EDUCATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN SCHOOLS Yulduzkhon S. Polvonova Mathematics Teacher, Creative School Named

After Ogahiy Under The Agency Of Presidential Educational Institutions Khiva, Uzbekistan

⁹ «Смешанное обучение: модели для применения в современной школе», Тулупникова Наталия Сергеевна, АВТОНОМНАЯ НЕКОММЕРЧЕСКАЯ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯ «НАУЧНО-ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫЙ ЦЕНТР ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ ПРОЕКТОВ» город Москва

study a new profile subject. At the same time, classes can be held both in person and using Internet platforms. This model was created in order to provide the necessary conditions for the study of a subject area that is not included in the general education program.

Inter-school group

A group of students engaged in the "Inter-school group" model is formed from students of various educational institutions of one or more municipalities who have expressed a desire to master the same subject remotely. The network teacher and the teacher-curator are appointed by the territorial coordinator of the municipal education department.

5. Individual curriculum.

A group of students engaged in the "IUP" model is formed on the basis of small cooperation groups typical of schools working according to individual curricula. In such schools, situations often arise when it is not possible to open a subject group in accordance with the educational needs of students due to its small number (less than 10 people). In such cases, an online learning group is created, which includes both students from OU working according to individual curricula, and students from other OU of this or other municipalities.

The "Personal Choice" and "Individual Curriculum" models can be characterized as follows:

Advantages	Disadvantages
Development of independence in a student;	The likelihood of problems with finding information on the Internet, due to technical problems;
Availability of information;	Lack of socialization of the student;
Full support from the teacher	

Conclusion.

Thus, this reform of the educational process has both positive and negative aspects. The considered technologies require high-quality technical equipment, training of teachers and personal responsibility of each student - in the absence of at least one of these factors, training will lose its meaning. However, with the successful use of these technologies, the quality of training increases due to the development of such a factor as independence and self-learning of students.

References

1. "A History of Teaching Machines" Ludy T. Benjamin, Jr Texas A&M University.
2. THE journal. "Computers in Education: A Brief History."
3. PLATO, computer-based education system. Steve Jones
4. «История развития образовательных моделей и технологий» Е.А. Алисов, Л.С. Подымова, Москва, Берлин 2021.
5. Inverted Classroom by Topic - A Study in Mathematics for Electrical Engineering Students,

PAPER INVERTED CLASSROOM BY TOPIC – A STUDY IN MATHEMATICS FOR ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING STUDENTS, I. Braun, S. Ritter and M. Vasko Karlsruhe University of Applied Sciences, Karlsruhe, Germany.

6. Технологические особенности модели "смена рабочих зон", <https://canvas.instructure.com/courses/1189709/pages/tiekhnologhichieskiie-osobiennosti-modieli-smiena-rabochikh-zon>

7. APPLICATION OF THE ROTATION MODEL FROM MIXED EDUCATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN SCHOOLS Yulduzhxon S. Polvonova Mathematics Teacher, Creative School Named After Ogahiy Under The Agency Of Presidential Educational Institutions Khiva, Uzbekistan

8. «Смешанное обучение: модели для применения в современной школе», Тулупникова Наталия Сергеевна, АВТОНОМНАЯ НЕКОММЕРЧЕСКАЯ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯ «НАУЧНО-ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫЙ ЦЕНТР ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ ПРОЕКТОВ» город Москва

COMMUNICATIVE METHOD OF TEACHING FRENCH AT THE UNIVERSITY

Jalalov F.

*Scientific researcher
Tashkent, Uzbekistan*

ABSTRACT

French language is a foreign language in Uzbekistan and that its teaching and learning cannot take the same process as acquiring first or a second language. In order to be able to interact with the native speakers in real life day to day communication, several techniques and methods should be used. Among French language learning methods, the leading position is occupied by the communicative approach, which is aimed directly at the development of communication. This study aims at analyzing the use of communicative method in teaching/learning process. It is proved that communicative approach makes it possible for students of the elementary level, not only to acquire the knowledge, but also to learn the socio-cultural component for adequate interaction with native French speakers in real-life situations. Findings of this study show that it is advisable for teachers of French language use the communicative language teaching approach to build confidence in their students, as this will help to develop faster their linguistic skills, given that this approach gives priority to listening and speaking skills over reading and writing skills.